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RESULTS OF COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN THE TREATMENT OF COVID-19 PNEUMONIA AND ITS COMPLICATIONS

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Annotation: In the course of the study, the changes in the lungs on CT during COVID-19 and after were analyzed, the main complications in various patients were identified, a connection was made between COVID-19 and symptoms such as turbidity of the "frosted glass" type, thickening of the septa, parenchymal formations, traction bronchiectasis and seals, etc.

Keywords: pneumonia, covid infection, diagnostics, computed tomography

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ПНЕВМОНИИ COVID-19 И ЕЕ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ

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Аннотация: В процессе исследования проанализированы изменения лёгких на КТ во время COVID-19 и после, выявлены основные осложнения у различных пациентов, проведена связь между COVID-19 и такими симптомами, как помутнения по типу «матового стекла», утолщение перегородок, паренхиматозные образования, тракционные бронхоэктазы и уплотнения и др.

Ключевые слова: пневмония, ковидная инфекция, диагностика, компьютерная томография

Relevance. Computed tomography of the chest plays an indispensable role in the management of patients with coronavirus disease (COVID-19). A significant number of patients who have had COVID-19 continue to experience its lingering symptoms even after recovery. Cough and shortness of breath are typical respiratory symptoms. It is very important to be aware of the changes in the pulmonary parenchyma that are observed in people who have had COVID-19 pneumonia, and to monitor the dynamics of the pathology. In addition, one should be aware of the peculiarities of visualization of pulmonary complications, which are often considered as direct consequences of COVID-19 [1].

The purpose of the work. To analyze the lung changes on CT during COVID-19 and after, to identify the main complications in various patients. To make a connection between COVID-19 and symptoms such as turbidity of the "frosted glass" type, thickening of the septa, parenchymal formations, traction bronchiectasis and seals, etc.

Materials and methods of research. The Pubmed database of scientific publications was used to search for materials. 41 scientific publications on the topic were selected for the period from 2019 to 2022. Statistical processing of the received data was performed on a personal computer using a set of standard statistical programs.

Results and their discussion. High-resolution computed tomography of the chest is considered one of the main methods for assessing the condition of the lungs after COVID-19. Computed tomography in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia revealed widespread persistent changes in the pulmonary parenchyma: foci of the "frosted glass" type, mesh formations, thickening of the septa, parenchymal formations

and traction bronchiectasis/bronchiolectasia; and rarely the formation of "honeycombs" [2-4].

When repeated computed tomography 3 weeks after the COVID-19, it turned out that about 50 % of patients completely disappeared traces of the disease. 40 % had persistent residual changes, of which the most common were fibrous formations and foci of the "frosted glass" type. These changes were observed on computed tomography 3 months, 6 months and 1 year after the disease.

Residual foci of the "frosted glass" type or interstitial thickening were observed in approximately 27 % of patients 6 months after the disease. A decrease in lung density was observed in several patients. Fibrous changes were detected in approximately 35 % of patients during 6 months of follow-up, and they included traction bronchiectasis, parenchymal and/or cellular formations [2].

Patients who developed fibrotic lung disease 6 months after suffering from COVID-19 pneumonia more often suffered from acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) during the acute phase and required artificial ventilation of the lungs. While the other group had complete resolution or only foci of the "frosted glass" type (without fibrous changes) [6].

Another study, which involved 118 patients who recovered from moderate to severe postcovid pneumonia, showed that 72 % of patients had fibrosis-like changes in chest CT after 6 months of follow-up. The most common anomaly was a persistent "frosted glass" symptom (in 42 % of patients), while thickening and consolidation of the septum were observed in 28 and 2 % of patients, respectively [3].

Complications of pneumonia after COVID-19:

Fungal infections. The most frequently reported fungal infections in patients recovered from COVID-19 are aspergillosis and lung mucormycosis [7].

The presence of cavitation, mass-like compaction, pleural effusion, nodules, the sign "halo", the sign "air crescent" and the sign "reverse halo" on the computed tomography of the chest are signs of fungal infections in patients who have undergone COVID-19. Characteristic signs of invasive fungal infections on computed tomography of the chest in patients who have not had COVID-19 include "frosted glass" syndrome, lobular consolidation, nodules (<3 cm), mass-like consolidation (>3 cm), "halo"

sign, "air crescent" sign, cavities and "reverse halo" sign. The presence of signs of "reverse halo", pleural effusion and concomitant infection of the sinuses indicate lung mucormycosis associated with COVID-19, while the presence of peribronchial consolidation, thickening of the bronchial wall and clusters of central lobular nodules indicates lung aspergillosis associated with COVID-19. However, in many cases, imaging alone may not be enough to differentiate between different fungal pneumonia, and a laboratory diagnosis is needed to confirm. There are also vascular complications, such as pseudoaneurysms, in patients with fungal infections associated with COVID-19 [4].

Bacterial infections. Patients with COVID-19 are more vulnerable to the development of additional bacterial infections. Concomitant bacterial infections during the acute phase of COVID-19 are most often caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pneumococcus* and *Hemophilus bacillus*. Some vulnerable patients remain prone to contracting these infections even after recovery. Due to the increased use of artificial ventilation during this pandemic, one of the additional complications of the phenomenon is pneumonia associated with artificial ventilation. It turned out that the incidence of pneumonia associated with artificial lung ventilation was significantly higher in patients with COVID-19 compared to patients in the intensive care unit without COVID-19 who were on artificial lung ventilation [3].

Identification of bacterial infection overlays during imaging in patients with pneumonia after COVID-19 may be difficult due to changes in lung parenchyma. However, the presence of nodules, compaction and cavitation on a CT scan of the chest should cause suspicion of additional infections. It is difficult to distinguish between bacterial and fungal lung infections based on visualization alone. The presence of random nodules, a sign of "reverse halo", cavitation and concomitant infection of the sinuses is a sign of fungal infections, while the presence of lobular areas of compaction, centrilobular nodules and pleural effusion are bacterial infections [7, 8].

Pulmonary embolism. COVID-19 is a procoagulant disease caused by a cytokine storm and localized pulmonary microangiopathy initiated by a virus in the body, which predisposes to venous thromboembolism. It was found that the risk of thrombosis in the pulmonary vessels persists even at the stage of postoperative recovery, at least up to 4 weeks. Computed

tomography of the lungs is the method of choice for examining patients with suspected thromboembolism [3].

Pneumothorax. Spontaneous pneumothorax in patients hospitalized with COVID-19 occurs with a frequency of 1.7 %. Pneumothorax may be associated with concomitant pneumomediastinum. In patients who develop pneumomediastinum and/or pneumothorax, artificial ventilation of the lungs is not performed due to the presence of cysts / bullae in the lungs and ischemic inflammatory damage to the lung parenchyma caused by the virus. Recently, many cases of spontaneous pneumothorax have been reported in patients who recovered from pneumonia caused by COVID-19 [5].

Conclusions. 60 % of patients after recovery from COVID-19 continue to experience the effects of the disease, which can last for weeks or even months. The lungs, being the most frequently affected organ of COVID-19, are the main target of the disease, and therefore it is extremely important to be aware of the progression of changes in the pulmonary parenchyma over time. Computed tomography of the chest is the preferred method for assessing the condition of the lungs after COVID. Persistent opacities of the "frosted glass" type, thickening of the septa, parenchymal formations, traction bronchiectasis and seals are the most common phenomena observed on computed tomography of the lungs after COVID-19.

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